
A350044

A PREPRINT

Eduardo J. Acuña T.
eduardonumberst9@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Loop starting at 187 in the Collatz-like map $x \rightarrow 3x + 5$ if x is odd, $x/2$ otherwise.

1 Introduction

The sequence A350044, is a numerical sequence describing a loop within which I am an author and was published in OEIS on 22/12/2021.

Repeats every forty-four terms starting at 187. Although other loops exist for the " $3x + 5$ " map, including $5 \rightarrow 20 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 5$ and $19 \rightarrow 62 \rightarrow 31 \rightarrow 98 \rightarrow 49 \rightarrow 152 \rightarrow 76 \rightarrow 38 \rightarrow 19$, this loop is much longer and does not appear in the trajectories of as many numbers.

If the Collatz conjecture is false, it will most likely fail because of the existence of a long loop. [1]

2 Sequence A350044

The numbers that make up the sequence are as follows.

187,	566,	283,	854,	427,	1286,	643,	1934,	967,	2906,	1453,
4364,	2182,	1091,	3278,	1639,	4922,	2461,	7388,	3694,	1847,	5546,
2773,	8324,	4162,	2081,	6248,	3124,	1562,	781,	2348,	1174,	587,
1766,	883,	2654,	1327,	3986,	1993,	5984,	2992,	1496,	748,	374

As it is a loop after 374 it goes to 187 and starts again.

3 FORMULA

The formula is from the sequence A18762.[2]

Where A18762 is:

$$a(n) = (7 * n + 10 - 10 * (-1)^n * (n/2 + 1))/4. \text{ -- Paolo P. Lava, Mar 10 2011}$$

$$G.f. : -x * (-8 - x + 2 * x^2)/((x - 1)^2 * (1 + x)^2). \text{ -- R. J. Mathar, Mar 10 2011}$$

So

$$a(n') = A181762(a(n - 1)) \text{ for } n > 1, \text{ with } a(1) = 187. \tag{1}$$

4 An MATHEMATICA algorithm

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a[1] = 187; a[n_]= a[n] = If[OddQ[a[n - 1]], 3*a[n - 1] + 5, a[n - 1]/2]; Array[a, 50]
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5 Some Graphics

Figure 1: A350044

Bibliography

- [1] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021). The on-line encyclopedia of integer sequences.<http://oeis.org/A350044>.
- [2] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021). The on-line encyclopedia of integer sequences.<http://oeis.org/A181762>.
- [3] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021). The on-line encyclopedia of integer sequences.<http://oeis.org/A344583>.